

Minutes of the 57th Experimenters' Meeting

The Cosener's House, Abingdon, Wednesday 29th June 2016

(This document was finalised on 2nd February 2017)

Present:

(CFL)	Dr Chris Lee ⁶	
(CJW)	Dr Chris Walden ⁴	
(DAH)	Dr David Hooper ^{3,4}	Secretary
(DK)	Dr Dirk Klugmann ⁴	
(GM)	Mr Graeme Marlton ⁶	
(GV)	Prof Geraint Vaughan ⁵	Chair
(KEW)	Miss Kate Winfield ^{2,4}	
(LD)	Mr Les Dean ^{1,3}	

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²Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA)

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Other abbreviations used in this document:

BLWP	Boundary-Layer Wind-Profiler
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EUCOS	EUMETNET Composite Observing System
GAP	Graham Parton (CEDA Data Scientist)
MST(R)(F)	Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
PV	Potential Vorticity
RMS	Root Mean Square
STFC	Science and Technology Facilities Council
UPS	Uninterruptable Power Supply
UT	Universal Time

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

GV thought that the following in section 4a had misrepresented his point of view: "*He [GV] felt that it was better to release the data first and then to worry about flagging up problems. The alternative is to only release data after checks had been carried out.*" He clarified that he thought it was important for users to be able to access the latest data as soon as possible. However, if no quality control checks had been carried out, or if more would eventually be needed, it is important that the files are labelled appropriately so that this is obvious.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 47.2.1 DAH to modify the MST radar signal processing software, as soon as possible, to allow it to make use of updated Python programming libraries.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 47.2.2 DAH to ensure, as soon as possible, that MST radar data products generated by the latest version of the signal processing software are available for the entire observation archive.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 51.4.1 DAH to increase the storage capacity of the Frongoch data logger so that communications failures do not lead to data loss.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 51.6.1 DAH to determine an improved method of applying the horizontal wind θ_s compensation factor so that its contribution to random errors is minimised.

ONGOING

DAH reported that no progress had been made on the 4 items above, i.e. 47.2.1, 47.2.2, 51.4.1, and 51.6.1.

ACTION ITEM 47.3.2 DAH to recreate cloud base altitude files, starting from 2nd November 2010, with the time stamps corrected.

ONGOING

DAH reported that his forthcoming vacation student - see section 3d - would need to make use of the laser ceilometer data. Consequently he had made some progress on the timing issue.

ACTION ITEM 53.3.2 DAH to review security measures for the MST Radar site and to make improvements where necessary.

COMPLETED

GV thought that the measures in place were appropriate and that this action item could be considered to be completed.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.2 DAH to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar permanently available to users if the Met Office will allow this.

ONGOING

DAH reported that a mechanism existed for adding such metadata into the CEDA archive.

ACTION ITEM 53.4.2 GAP and DAH to determine a way of providing retrospectively-determined data reliability details in a machine-readable format.

ONGOING

DAH reported that the CHARMe system that he and Graham Parton (GAP) had been looking into was probably not appropriate for this purpose. He thought that a simple lookup file containing the start and end date-times of instrument issues - e.g. when the tipping bucket rain gauge is not thought to be working or when one or more MST radar transmitters are down - might be the best solution. He has used such a solution in his operational software for the Campbell Scientific surface met instruments in order to blank precipitation data for periods when the sensor has been cleaned.

ACTION ITEM 56.3.1 GAP to report on how DOIs can be assigned to datasets at the 57th Experimenters' meeting.

COMPLETED

KEW will deliver this report, on GAP's behalf, in section 3a.

GV expressed his concern that the MST radar signal processing action (51.6.1) kept getting pushed back by other work. He recognised that some of the issues - e.g. determining the appropriate time scale for averaging winds - had been solved. However, there was still no sign of a new processing scheme. He insisted that DAH and CJW put together a plan to ensure that the work is completed in time for the next Experimenters' meeting.

ACTION ITEM 57.1.1 DAH and CJW to put together a work plan to ensure that a new MST radar signal processing scheme is ready by the time of the next (58th) Experimenters' meeting.

NEW

3. Facility Report - DAH

Full details of facility and instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

3a) Data Management

KEW gave a report on behalf of GAP, who was unable to attend the meeting. She began by explaining how Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) can be assigned to datasets - i.e. addressing Action Item 56.3.1. DOIs are used to provide a permanent reference to digital objects - mostly to journal articles. CEDA is able to "mint" DOIs for datasets, in which case they direct to the relevant CEDA catalogue pages. Once a DOI has been issued, certain metadata fields - e.g. the title, the names of the author(s) and the publisher, and the date of publication - may not be changed. Moreover, no changes may be made to the files once they enter the dataset. However, it is still possible to update other details on the catalogue page and to add new files to the dataset as they become available.

DAH has already made changes to the way in which MST radar Cartesian files are delivered to the CEDA archives in order to conform to these requirements. The files are initially delivered to a "quarantine" area (on the jasmin system) outside of the archive. DAH only releases them once he has seen the quick look plots and is satisfied that there are no obvious problems with the data. Although this increases the length of time before the files become openly available (typically a few hours on weekdays, but a few days over weekends), it avoids the complications arising from having to remove a file from the archive.

There was a general feeling that users should be able to access the very latest data, irrespective of whether or not they had passed the final quality control checks. Examples were given of other datasets that could be available for a year or more before quality control and/or calibration data were made available. Version numbers are often included within file names in order to differentiate the different releases.

There was also some discussion of the need to have retrospectively-determined reliability details in a machine-readable format (i.e. Action Item 53.4.2). This was thought to be particularly important now that users are starting to access the dataset through the open access route rather than going through the Facility.

3b) Electricity - DAH

As usual, the Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units suffered brief (i.e. of the order of 1 s) problems with the electricity supply on a number of occasions. The TX5 unit reported a faulty battery as a result of the self test carried out on 3rd February 2016. Owing to the length of time that it took to set up a contract with a supplier, a replacement battery pack was not delivered until 8th March. Consequently the transmitter for antenna section E remained out of action for two weeks following an input power problem on 25th February 2016, which caused the unit to fail. Although LD tried to switch the transmit-

ter to the UPS unit for the adjacent transmitter, the combined load was too great for one unit. Since the new battery pack has been installed, it has sent a large number of “critical” system messages warning that the unit has carried out a “warmstart”. As far as DAH can tell, this refers to the unit’s network card briefly losing site of the internet. One of the other units used to occasionally give the same message. All of the UPS units reported unusually long input power problems on 27th May 2016 (25 s) and on 26th April and 19th June (150 s). There were scheduled, day-long outages of power for the whole Capel Dewi area on 22nd February and 12 April 2016. This was to allow the local distribution company to carry out essential work.

3c) Telecommunications

The internet connection to the site was lost in the late afternoon of Friday 27th May 2016. This was apparently the result of nearby thunderstorms. Since this was a Bank Holiday weekend and LD happened to be away, the connection remained out of action until the following Tuesday morning (31st May). It was re-established after Dave Wareing changed the phone/broadband filter and switched to the backup router. DAH installed a new router when he visited the radar site on 9th June 2016.

3d) Miscellaneous

GV reported on the National Capability evaluation exercise that was recently undertaken by NERC. The MSTRF came out of this well. However, the stated purpose of the exercise was simply to establish whether or not each Facility was actually delivering what it said it would. NERC must now decide which of its facilities it aims to continue to fund. It will seek input from members of the user communities. The MSTRF’s main weakness is its small number of registered users. However, this situation has improved slightly owing to the increasing number of people relying on the open access route to the data. The Facility will need to think boldly about the direction in which it proposes to develop. Some of the ideas being considered include a merger with the Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR) and transferring some of the MSTRF’s budget from the research stream to the long term science funding stream. DAH should also think about what new equipment would be useful should funding be renewed.

DAH reported that income from Met Office for the provision of MST radar wind-profile data has been reduced for the current financial year. This is a result of the Met Office being obliged to make large savings across their budget. Their plans for the following financial year are not yet known.

The MSTRF has recently (March 2016) purchased solid state transmitter modules, with a peak power of 40 kW, and a new radar control/data acquisition system. The timing of the purchase was forced by the fact that the MSTRF can no longer roll over any unspent income from the Met Office from one financial year to the next. This is the result of the Met Office and the Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC) now being under the same government department. The existing transmitters are thought to have a combined peak output power of 100 kW. Consequently there are no plans to install the new modules in the immediate future. A strategy for installing the new equipment will only be formulated once the outcome of the forthcoming NERC funding renewal procedure is known. GV asked DAH to draw up a short development plan for the radar in the context of funding renewal.

ACTION ITEM 57.3.1 DAH to write a short MST radar development plan in time for a meeting with GV later in the summer.

NEW

DAH has been encountering difficulties setting up contracts to get estates work - e.g. grass cutting and electrical repairs - done at the radar site. This is the result of the government’s “Facilities Management” rules, which came into effect in 2016. These are designed to channel all estates work through central suppliers.

There has not been much explicit interest in the MSTRF from the “chemtrail” conspiracy theory community over the past 6 months. Nevertheless, someone has recently posted photographs of the site on a Facebook page after making a visit during the early hours of a morning in late May 2016.

There have been a number of official visits to the site over the past 6 months. MSc students from Aberystwyth University visited on 3rd March 2016 in order to carry out a surveying exercise on the antenna array. Environmental science students from the University of Manchester visited on 4th April. This was part of a wider study visit to mid Wales. Members of the Aberystwyth amateur radio club visited the site on 9th June. They were very interested in the hardware, which was shown off to them by LD. DAH gave them a short presentation on atmospheric refractive index beforehand. Members of GV's group from the University of Manchester visited the following day (10th June).

Finally, DAH will host a Vacation Student over the summer, i.e. someone who is part way through their (Physics) degree course. Their job will be to compare rain measurements made by the different instruments at the site - primarily the tipping bucket rain gauge and the piezo electric sensor (on the Vaisala WXT510/WXT520). They will also consider the precipitation detection flags provided by the LD40 laser ceilometer and the MST radar.

4. NERC Instrument Report - DAH

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

NASA Ames data files and quick look plots have not been made available through CEDA since DAH was obliged to move the processing software to the jasmin system in late 2015. Nevertheless, the raw data are being recorded and the new software is almost ready for use. DAH has written in the ability to blank rainfall measurements for periods when the instrument is being cleaned. He has discovered that in addition to the integrated rainfall within each 10 minute period, the raw data logs also contain the time (to the nearest minute) of the peak rain rate. This information is not available in the NASA Ames files, but is potentially useful.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

There is nothing to report for this instrument over the past 6 months.

4c) Vaisala WXT520 surface met and wind sensors

Data files and quick look plots for this instrument have not been made available since it replaced the WXT510 in April 2015. They will follow after the data feeds for the other instruments have been restarted. DAH drew attention to the fact that this instrument (and the WXT510 that preceded it) measure hail as well as rain.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

DAH showed examples of backscatter data produced by this instrument. They reveal a lot more about the atmosphere than the cloud base data that are derived from them. So far, only the latter have been made publicly available. DAH is keen to release the backscatter data, but must first produce a software solution to infer observation times. The time stamps in the raw data files are produced by a free running internal clock, which drifts substantially and is reset whenever the power has been resumed. DAH was particularly interested in the backscatter data for 20th June 2016, which show an isolated high-level cloud between 21 and 24 UT. This appears to be the source of turbulence seen by the MST radar.

4e) Sky Camera 2

DAH will begin to release images from this instrument, which has been in operation since March 2015, once he has derived its pointing direction. This information can then be embedded within the image files using the Dublin Core metadata scheme. DAH is also due to start releasing time-lapse videos derived

from images taken by the original Sky Camera. Video files have a more restricted capacity for metadata than image files and the wmv file type only allows 5 fields to be embedded: title, author, copyright, comment, and rating. DAH is in the process of designing the title plate that will precede each time lapse sequence. The title plate will display the same metadata that have been embedded.

4f) Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) Camera

Images are once more being collected at 5 minute intervals for the summer season, i.e. during June and July. The camera detected a weak display of NLCs during the morning of 19th June 2016. DAH needs to determine the pointing direction for this camera as well so that the information can be embedded with the image files.

4g) MST Radar

DAH began by presenting model-comparison statistics, which had been prepared by Caroline Bulpett of the Met Office. The number of observations received daily by the EUMETNET Composite Observing System (EUCOS) has remained fairly constant over the period. There were only a few days when this dropped significantly and these were associated with known internet problems. The EUCOS root mean square (RMS) wind mean vector difference values were only rarely above the 5.0 m s^{-1} target maximum. As expected, there was more of a spread in the RMS direction differences. The Met Office's UKV model-comparison statistics also show good data quality over the period. The largest RMS wind component differences were seen in May 2016, when jet stream activity was most prevalent.

DAH then gave a general instrument performance report. The radar encountered a new form of interference for the first time on 4th May 2016. It manifested itself at altitudes of around 10 km in the form of slightly-enhanced signal powers, horizontal wind speeds of near zero, and enhanced spectral widths. These characteristics suggest that all beam pointing directions were affected. It was seen again intermittently over the following week and then was absent until 27th June 2016, when it covered a much wider altitude region. DAH is unsure of the cause.

The radar has suffered from occasional periods when one of the transmitters is out of action. This occurred only once (on 4th March 2016) for the transmitter powering antenna sector A. It was the result of a short-lived analogue error. The transmitter for antenna sector B had a blown fuse on 7 occasions, 4 of which occurred during February 2016. The transmitter for antenna sector C had a blown fuse on 4 occasions, and the transmitter for antenna sector E just once.

Beam steering units 81, 82, 91, and 92, which are all fed from the same power divider in antenna sector E, alternated between being unresponsive and responsive on 26th February 2016. LD replaced one of the N-type connectors, which was found to be in a degraded state. Unit 30 alternated between indicating a low supply voltage and a normal one on a large number of occasions on 2nd and 3rd March 2016. LD replaced it on the afternoon of 3rd March, when the radar was down for a surveying practical (see section 3d). Unit 2 began to suffer from the same problem on 10th April 2016. LD replaced it on the 12th, when the radar was down for other reasons. LD replaced unit 30 again on 19th April after it suffered a recurrence of the supply voltage problem.

5. Guest Instrument Report - GV

The boundary-layer wind-profiler (BLWP) is still on deployment at Heathrow Airport, although it is not currently working. It has suffered from problems with both its power supply and its communications. It will return to Capel Dewi in August or September 2016 and will probably remain there until the spring of 2017. The water vapour lidar is currently working well. It detected high concentrations of free tropospheric aerosol on 24th and 25th May 2016. These are thought to have been transported from forest fires in Canada. GV noted that the Met Office have an archive of quick-look plots from their Jenoptik lidars. He was interested in the observations made from Aberporth for this event. He has asked CEDA to try to provide access to these in addition to the data files, which are already available. Although,

the Jenoptik (infra-red) instruments are not calibrated, unlike the (ultra-violet) lidar at Capel Dewi, it would be useful to have access to an additional source of observations. The SAOZ ozone instrument has suffered from a number of problems recently. Although it is currently working, its performance is not as good as it was before it was sent back to France for maintenance work.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) Measuring turbulence with adapted radiosondes and comparison with the NERC MST Radar - GM

As part of his PhD work, GM launched 18 specially-adapted radiosondes from the MST Radar site. These carried accelerometers, which give a measure of the swinging motion of the radiosonde beneath its balloon. The assumption is that this motion is initiated by the radiosonde package encountering changes in wind speed and/or direction. Consequently, the accelerations are assumed to give a measure of turbulence intensity. The radiosondes were mostly launched during periods when the jet stream was overhead. They did not encounter any clear instances of mountain wave breaking.

GM has been using radar spectral widths from beams directed at 6.0° off-vertical. These have been corrected for the effects of beam broadening. However, this sometimes results in negative values of the square of the corrected width. This has been dealt with by Dehghan et al. (2014) - <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jastp.2013.10.009> - by first averaging the squares of the corrected values and by Nastrom and Eaton (1997) - <http://dx.doi.org/10.1029/97JD01262> - by using median values. GM has opted to use variable weighting which decreases the influence of over-corrected values when averaging over one hour. These values are then averaged over a vertical interval of 1.5 km and compared with the standard deviations of the accelerometer readings over the same interval. The correlation between these two sets of values varied from case to case. It tended to be better for times when there was a jet stream overhead.

There are additional problems in knowing the best way to convert the corrected radar spectral widths to eddy dissipation rates. GM has avoided a method that relies on knowing the inner and outer scales of turbulence, since neither is known with certainty (CFL commented that the outer scale of turbulence needs to be smaller than the radar pulse volume in order for the largest eddies to be fully incorporated). He has instead focused on a method that relies on knowledge of the Brunt-Väisälä frequency and on the value of an empirically derived constant. He has also investigated a more complex method that uses a confluent hypergeometric function to represent the pulse volume. The second method results in a stronger linear relationship with accelerometer standard deviations, but values that are smaller by an order of magnitude.

GV drew GM's attention to turbulence papers by Shaun Lovejoy with Adrian Tuck - <http://www.physics.mcgill.ca/~gang/reference.list.htm> - which consider the atmosphere from a fractal point of view. Observational data were taken from dropsondes, which avoid the wake issues inherent in radiosonde flights.

6b) North Atlantic Waveguide and Downstream Impact Experiment (NAWDEX) - GV

This large, international campaign will be conducted between 19th September and 16th October 2016. The central hypothesis is that diabatic processes over North America and the North Atlantic have a major influence on subsequent meanders in the jet stream and hence on the weather over Europe. The diabatic heating in rising air lifts low potential vorticity (PV) air towards the tropopause region. This results in an enhanced vertical PV gradient across the tropopause/jet stream, which increases the phase speed of Rossby waves on the upstream side. On the downstream side, i.e. towards Europe, this leads to Rossby wave breaking, cyclonic development, anomalous low-level flows of moisture, and high impact weather.

The German Halo and Falcon aircraft will be based in Iceland and will rely on remote sensing of the

regions of interest. A number of instruments will be operated at the MST Radar site as a downstream location. Radiosondes will be launched every two hours during intensive observation periods. The Raman lidar will be used for water vapour and static stability measurements. The ozone lidar will be used to determine ozone concentrations around the jet stream. The BLWP and Elight lidar will be used to capture low-level structures. The MST radar observations will be used primarily to study the structure of the tropopause and the jet stream. Knowledge of turbulence and inertia-gravity wave activity will also be of use. Hugo Ricketts and Bogdan Antonescu will also be involved in these measurements.

7. Any Other Business

DK gave a report on how science research funding can potentially be obtained through the UK's Official Development Assistance (ODA) scheme. The projects need to demonstrate that they can provide benefits both to the UK and to a developing partner country. Suitable subject areas include agriculture, human health, air quality, and education. The Newton fund covers all research councils. It has very strict requirements, including that the project receives matched funding from another source. The Global Challenges Research Fund (GCRF), which is specific to STFC, does not require matched funding and so has a better scope for being used to initiate partnerships. GV commented that although NERC should be well placed for this type of scheme, since it already focuses on impact, it has not yet developed anything similar.

The date of the next Experimenters' meeting was provisionally set for late January 2017.